

FDI REFERENCES FOR EFFECTIVE ECONOMIC INTEGRATION AND COUNTRY COMPETITIVENESS

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Abstract. Developing and improving the competitiveness of the Moldovan economy in terms of economic integration is impossible without the development of an effective investment policy. In this article, the author proposed to develop innovative proposals and recommendations for improving the country's investment sector, through modernization of infrastructure, tax incentives, selective stimulation of investment in certain enterprises transparency and integrity of capital, guarantees and protection of rights of foreign investors based on improved national legislative framework features of formation and study ways of further development of the investment sector of the Republic of Moldova, through a new investment policy based on national interests and national security, coordination of credit and financial system, and material production as well as the proposed measures on the functioning of the Programme of investment activity in order to achieve economic growth in the national economy.

Keywords: foreign direct investment, economic integration, investment climate, security, competitiveness

REFERINȚE ISD PENTRU INTEGRAREA ECONOMICĂ EFICIENTĂ ȘI COMPETITIVITATEA ȚĂRII

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Rezumat. Dezvoltarea și ridicarea nivelului competitivității economiei moldovenești în condițiile integrării economice nu este posibilă fără elaborarea unei politici investiționale eficiente a țării. În prezentul articol se expun propunerile inovaționale și recomandările, elaborate de către autor, pentru perfecționarea ariei investiționale a țării prin modernizarea infrastructurii, privilegiile de impozitare, stimularea selectivă ale investițiilor capitale în întreprinderi determinate, transparența și

integritatea capitalului, garanțiile și protejarea drepturilor investitorilor străini în baza cadrului legal național îmbunătățit; particularitățile devenirii și fundamentarea căilor de dezvoltare în continuarea a domeniului investițional din Republica Moldova, prin prisma noii politici investiționale în baza intereselor naționale comune și securității statului, coordonarea acțiunilor ariilor creditare financiare și a producerii materiale, la fel a măsurilor propuse pentru funcționarea Programului dezvoltării activității investiționale întru obținerea creșterii economice în economia națională.

Cuvintele cheie: investiții străine directe, integrarea economică, climatul investițional, securitatea națională, competitivitatea.

Introduction. In order to ensure effective economic integration of the Republic of Moldova, the priority direction of the state policy should be the orderly application of the strategy of attracting foreign direct investment in the country's economy. Thus, the policy of state regulation of foreign investment should include certain legal norms and measures to ensure foreign investors' access to the domestic market, streamline the volume of foreign investors' investments in the authorized capital of joint ventures, establish preferential regimes and eliminate administrative obstacles.

Legislation should maximally equalize foreign legal entities with local ones, provide a number of significant guarantees at the level of the law, thus creating all the prerequisites for improving investment conditions in the Republic of Moldova. The measures taken to create a favorable investment climate for FDI inflows into the country's economy should be regarded as insufficient. The general socio-economic and political situation of the country remains unstable, therefore, in this situation, the implementation of laws may be ineffective, which predetermines the need for constant updating of the legislation of the Republic of Moldova in the field of foreign direct investment and bringing it into line with European standards.

Therefore, one of the main tasks in a set of measures to improve the efficiency of the investment process is the selection and justification of priority areas and measures in demand by practice for the import of capital. They should stimulate the initiative to attract FDI for the following reasons: it is necessary to establish economic policy goals and indicative indicators that can also become guidelines for corporate governance; it is necessary to identify bottlenecks and provide an opportunity to develop appropriate preventive measures in time; the government needs to involve business in the problems of economic policy, analyze and select various investment projects that have, first of all, national interests.

Undoubtedly, the investment policy of the state is increasingly influenced by a huge number of voluntary standards of corporate social responsibility. The government can maximize development benefits from these standards by

implementing appropriate policies, such as harmonizing corporate reporting requirements, adopting capacity building programs and integrating corporate social responsibility standards into international investment regimes. Undoubtedly, these initiatives will help create favorable conditions for attracting foreign investment.

Main text. A characteristic trend that determines the development of the foreign investment market in modern conditions is the implementation by national governments and international organizations of a policy of liberalization of the international investment space, the development of universal norms for investment cooperation. For the national economy, with a constant deficit of its own financial resources, which hinders sustainable economic development, the priority is the inflow of foreign direct investment, especially in the development of production potential, which is the determining source for the process of modernization based on innovative technologies and solving the accumulated problems of socio-economic development.

An important factor in the development of the economy in the context of effective economic integration is the increase in the investment attractiveness of the Republic of Moldova and the growth of foreign investment, which in turn should contribute to the modernization of the economy, increase the competitiveness of Moldovan products and increase their exports, including to the EU countries. Thus, for the effective economic integration of the country and increasing its competitiveness, we consider it necessary to offer the following references and recommendations for attracting foreign direct investment in the economy of the Republic of Moldova:

1. Modernize state regulation of the real and financial sectors of the national economy based on the introduction of indicative planning and operational monitoring of investment activity, while MIEPO needs to monitor and find out which enterprises are ready to use FDI, which enterprises have created conditions for attracting FDI, which enterprises have potential for working with foreign direct investment.

2. The Government of the Republic of Moldova needs to solve the problem of concentration of production and restructuring of enterprises, especially in the agro-industrial complex, processing industry, logistics, including using recommendations to increase the attractiveness for foreign investors of these particular areas of the economy that form its basis.

3. The Government of the Republic of Moldova, together with MIEPO, develop and implement program actions to restore the attractiveness of investments for foreign investors in the real sector of the economy (fixed capital). In this regard, it is necessary to create conditions for transparency and competition for all foreign

investors, in terms of specific actions, the Ministry of Economy is invited to play a tender for the acceptance of FDI in the Republic of Moldova, to develop investment priorities, and to develop a mechanism for the transfer of capital from less efficient to more efficient advanced industries.

4. We recommend that the Government of the Republic of Moldova conduct selective incentives for investment in certain enterprises, industries and areas of innovation through credit and tax incentives, in particular with the help of an investment loan, as well as regulate the total amount of investment by private businesses (stimulation or restriction). In this regard, we propose to use the following tax incentives that stimulate the investment process: tax credit, tax rebates, tax subsidies.

5. We recommend that MIEPO develop a Program for attracting FDI to innovative sectors of the economy (processing industry, environmental protection, telecommunications) of the Republic of Moldova, taking into account the change in tax policy (providing tax incentives) in terms of returning to a zero tax rate on the income of economic agents and other norms, stimulating entrepreneurial activity and FDI inflows, as well as future prospects for the development of this area.

6. The Government of the Republic of Moldova to improve the state regulation of investment activity and the legislative framework, which must be directed, first of all, to protect the rights of capital owners, to ensure the guarantee and inviolability of capital and private property, to ensure conditions for unhindered capital accumulation in the interests of capital owners, which, ultimately, it will positively affect the development of production, the growth of consumption and qualitative changes in the country's economy (economic growth).

7. On the basis of the logical-descriptive model for increasing the efficiency of foreign direct investment in the national economy, to recommend that specialists in the field of economic law use its provisions when developing a draft law of the Republic of Moldova regulating the FDI process.

8. We recommend that the government create and ensure the effective functioning of a national investment base in the form of a system of public and private corporations and investment funds to finance economic recovery programs, in particular, involve the banking system in solving this problem. The creation of such structures will improve the mechanism for attracting FDI and their quantitative and qualitative impact on the economic growth of the Republic of Moldova, and as a result, successful economic integration.

9. Create a structure and develop a program aimed at the sustainable, dynamic development of the real sector of the national economy, combined with measures to modernize it, as well as the preservation and development of the

scientific and production potential of the country, the formation of industrial and scientific and technical policy on this basis, ensuring their implementation through the use of state guarantees, the implementation of targeted investment and scientific and technical programs based on indicative planning and stimulation of investment and innovation activity.

10. The Parliamentary Economic Commission to develop a science-based industry catalog for foreign investors, dividing objects for foreign investment into four categories: encouraged; permitted; limited; prohibited; and also, to determine the priorities of technical and economic development in the main progressive areas, based on the patterns of long-term economic growth, global and national competitive advantages.

11. The Government of the Republic of Moldova to review the state approach to attracting foreign direct investment and introduce a new socially responsible investment (Socially responsible investing or SRI, sustainable, socially-conscious, or ethical investing) carried out by the investor, taking into account the social, moral and environmental consequences for the recipient country . In particular, to make additions to Article 20 of the Law “On Investments in Entrepreneurial Activities” No. 81-XV of March 18, 2004.

12. Resolve the issue of regional representatives of the central government in the field of state regulation of regional investment activity, the purpose of which is to increase the role and responsibility of the regions in making and implementing investment decisions, while reducing the number of controlling state bodies and coordinating their activities by a specialized unit within the Ministry of Economy.

13. MIEPO under the auspices of the Ministry of Economy to develop indicators of the level of ensuring national security in the implementation of investment policy, while it is necessary to single out several groups of indicators that provide different levels of national security: economic, innovation, investment.

14. Reduce the number of economic activities that require licensing and ensure fair competition in the domestic market of the country, using the best practices of different countries.

15. Ensure equal conditions and protection of the rights of foreign investors, regardless of the volume of investments and the country of origin of capital.

Conclusion: Foreign direct investment should now become a priority and they need to play an important role as an integral part of the national development strategy, as the most important prerequisite for long-term economic stability, economic integration of the country, and as a result, increasing the competitiveness of the national economy in the international market. To achieve this goal, serious

efforts are needed to change the current trend in competition in the international investment market, use market resources to develop the economy at a new technological level, more effectively involve the country in international integration processes and in the world market economy.

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